

EUPHEMISMS IN POLITICAL DISCOURSE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7663172>

ELSEVIER

Foundation of Advanced Research Sciences

Ruziyeva Nafisa Zarifovna

Independent Researcher of Bukhara State University

Abstract: In the 21st century, we can think of words as a kind of "weapon," a way to influence others, accomplish our goals, or even express ourselves. Even though we live in a time when words like "freedom of speech" and "equality" encourage us to say and do what we want, there are still prohibitions and taboos, as well as words that are considered to be unpleasant, harsh, or offensive by society. A word or phrase that replaces a taboo word or avoids unpleasant or offensive plots is known as a euphemism. The euphemism is used to bring the conversation together and make it pleasant and easy.

Keywords: euphemisms, Political correct words, political discourse, polite words.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Received: 21-02-2023

Accepted: 22-02-2023

Published: 22-02-2023

Discourse is a form of speech communication that aims to gain public support and agreement by addressing pressing and significant issues and expressing one's thoughts, opinions, and positions. In this case, discourse takes on an ideological bent and actually becomes political. Because it is a means of achieving social peaceful consent, political discourse plays an important role in the conditions of politics.

Although the discursive approach is relatively new in political science, its popularity is high due to the growing significance of language in society [8]. In addition, with the rapid growth of mass media, language has been used to influence and manipulate individuals. Society and language are inextricably linked: Language is also the primary tool for comprehending political phenomena and is influenced by its native speakers. Because language has a significant impact on political communication, as reflected in media texts, political communication has a significant impact on citizens' public consciousness and shapes their political views and positions.

As a result, political discourse includes, among other things, the selection of topics that become the subject of discussion and the language used to discuss these topics. Therefore, not only is it essential to select a topic that is appropriate for political discourse but also to properly present it. The struggle for power, the defense of one's word, and one's rights are the primary objectives of political communication; consequently, the concepts of "power" and "politics" represent the fundamental concepts of political discourse. The ability, the right, the possibility of coercion, the imposition of one's opinion, and subsequent evidence of one's

rightness and conviction are all included in the concept of "power." The slogans of statements, the declamatory style of the appeal, the intensification of opponents' criticism, the ideologization of the topic under discussion, oratorical and agitational enthusiasm, and overconfidence in one's own opinion all reflect the evaluative and aggressive nature of political discourse.

The policy is aimed at forming a negative attitude towards the speaker's political opponents, imposing various values and assessments on them, and this is the main reason that terms positively described by one person are perceived negatively by his opponents. In other words, the goal is not just to describe the situation, but to convince of the correctness of their words, to cause the "right" action. It can be said that persuasion is one of the main features of political discourse. For a politician, the main goal is to touch the right chord in mass consciousness, to attract attention. Political discourse has certain requirements in order to be effective. Speakers on the political field are aimed at "destroying" opinions and views the opponent through arguments and opinions that emphasize the correctness of their position. The systematic features of political discourse are institutionality, specific informativeness, semantic uncertainty, the special role of the media actor, remoteness and authoritarianism, theatricality and dynamism. In political communication, the function of influence is important: it is the achievement of influence that a politician focuses on when choosing linguistic means. An important feature of political discourse is that politicians often try to disguise their goals by using various photographic lexical means, morphological categories, syntactic constructions, textual categories and other methods of influencing the minds of opponents.

As far as we know, the media is the most important and important source of information for our society. The main topic of many publications in newspapers and magazines is politics. All texts, publications and speeches devoted to politics relate to political discourse. Political discourse is characterized by the ability to manipulate people's minds. The purpose of this type of discourse is power. But in order to hide such intentions, most media outlets try to use such words or expressions in the texts of their publications that will not harm the feelings of other people, will not offend them, by others in other words, they use a politically correct one. There are a number of certain beliefs of political myths in people's minds that can be activated in order to influence the audience. Political euphemisms in the texts of political communication they are used to mitigate negative associations associated with certain facts, often by changing the meaning of the described fact itself. Political euphemisms are part of the vocabulary of general euphemisms, and the scope of their application in the language is related to the meaning of the term

"political": state power, public life, social issues, as well as public actions of politicians and officials.

Political euphemisms in political communication texts can be they are used for purposeful influence on the addressee of political communication. This is done by changing the assessment of certain phenomena, events, total replacement of concepts in some areas of life and is aimed at changing the ideological, ideological, political and moral views of the individual, i.e. it is ideological in nature. Another important feature of euphemisms is their close connection with the category of political correctness.

The work of N.V. Perfileva and D.N. Nikishina, based on the dictionary of V.N. Yartseva, shows how over time the trend towards political correctness spreads to other areas, and, as a result, currently English euphemisms can be divided into several thematic groups:

1. Euphemisms to mitigate discrimination in for people with physical and mental health problems: differently-abled "with other abilities" or physically challenged "a person overcoming difficulties due to his physical condition" instead of invalid "disabled"; "mentally retarded children" – "children with learning difficulties". In Uzbek, *aqli zaif, aqli yo'q, bir kam yuz, beaql, kallasi aynigan, nosog'roq, tomi yo'q, to'qson to'qqiz, ruhiy nosog'lom, oshqovoq, kallavaram*.

2. Euphemisms that mitigate age discrimination: showing the age of people, *senior citizens, third age, mature*. In Uzbek, *faxriy, oqsoqol, yoshuli, nuroniy, keksalik libosini kiygan, baxori tugamoq, oshini oshab, yoshini yashamoq*,

3. Euphemisms that mitigate racial discrimination: Native Americans are Indigenous people instead of Red Indians *Redskins*, for African people *mainber of African diaspora, indigenous person (negro, latino latina)*, for African and Asian people *Non-whites, correct society (having a proportionate ratio of blacks, whites, Hispanics)*,

4. Euphemisms replace the names of physical disabilities: *fat - people overcoming difficulties because of their horizontal proportions, overweight*; for short people - *people of low stature*. In Uzbek, expressing fat woman – *to'lachadan kelgan, do'mboq, do'ndiq, do'ndiqcha*.

5. Euphemisms used instead of words with gender morphemes, for example, -man and -ess: *chairman - chairperson, spokesman - spokesperson "representative", cameraman - camera operator, fireman - firefighter, stewardess or steward - flight attendant, postman - mail carrier, headmistress - headteacher "school principal"*.

6. Euphemisms related to the topic of death: *deceased* instead of *deadman, passed away, to go west for to die*. In Uzbek, *dunyodan o'tmoq, bandalikni bajo keltirmoq, halok bo'lmoq, qurbon bo'lmoq, oramizdan ketmoq*.

7. Euphemisms used to increase the prestige of some professions: *housekeeper, an Information Resource Officer (a librarian); public relations counsel, contact manager, publicist (press agent)*. In Uzbek, *obodonlashtirish xodimi, texnik xodim, kabinet mudiri*.

8. Euphemisms that mitigate negative phenomena in the socio-economic sphere of people's lives: *economically disadvantaged, low income, man of modest means, the less well off, the under privileged, in Uzbek, cheklangan mablag'lar, qo'li kalta, sharoiti yo'q, temir daftarga kiritilganlar, sharoiti og'ir.*

Political euphemisms are a subset of euphemisms that can be included in the larger phenomenon of euphemism, as previously mentioned. Therefore, we can assume that political euphemisms are directly related to the existence of political taboos and the subject areas of political taboos if euphemisms are used to replace the word "taboo." The following definition of political taboo is possible given the scope of the topic and the fact that political euphemisms are widely used in political communication texts. Words and phrases that should not be used in political communication are known as political taboos. These words and phrases can cause negative reactions or offend the feelings of any group or even the nation as a whole.

In conclusion, it is important to note that the terms "political euphemism" and "political correctness" are not only synonymous with one another but also have significant distinctions between them. Political correctness, which has recently been referred to as "ethical correctness," "communicative correctness," or "cultural correctness," is a term that refers primarily to language policy and a particular ideology of the state. The concept of political euphemism is primarily associated with language and its processes.

The researchers studying this phenomenon maintain that political correctness only applies to the "social" spheres. Its objective is to avoid disparaging any group of people. Political euphemism encompasses not only the "social" spheres but also the political, military, and other spheres. Its primary objective is to lessen the negative associations that are associated with particular facts, frequently by distorting the meaning of the fact that is being described.

The following conclusion ought to be reached after taking into consideration the characteristics of political language as well as political euphemism: To maintain a balance between two opposing trends, the texts of political communication have established the conditions for the widespread use of political euphemisms: the enactment of a deliberate orientation of political communication texts toward direct evaluation, propaganda, and persuasion, in addition to adherence to current social norms of cultural and legal correctness. Political correctness, which is implemented within the framework of politeness strategies, is one of the methods for countering verbal aggression and maintaining a positive attitude from the other person. The emerging communicative conflict can be resolved with the help of a well-chosen euphemism. In the age of widespread intercultural interaction and the resulting intercultural conflicts, this issue is becoming increasingly relevant.

REFERENCE:

1. Арутюнова Н. Д. Дискурс // Языкознание. Лингвистический энциклопедический словарь / гл. ред. В. Н. Ярцева. 1-е изд-е. М.: Большая Российская энциклопедия, 1990. – С. 136-137.
2. Гаврилова М. В. Лингвистический анализ политического дискурса. // Политический анализ. Доклады эмпирических политических исследований СПбГУ. СПб: СПбГУ, 2002. Вып.3. С.88–108. – URL: http://www.academia.edu/10309239/Лингвистический_анализ_политического_дискурса
3. Ильин М. В. Политический дискурс: слова и смыслы (Государство) // Вестник Московского государственного института международных отношений (университет). – 1994, – С.127–140. – URL: <http://bibliofond.ru/view.aspx?id=97555>
4. Карасик В. И. Языковой круг: личность, концепты, дискурс. М.: Гнозис, 2004. – 390 с
5. Милевская Т.В. Грамматика дискурса. Ростов-на-Дону, 2003. – 180 с.
6. Перфильева Н. В., Никишина Д.Н. Политические эвфемизмы лексикосемантической группы «терроризм» в СМИ // Вестник РУДН, серия Теория языка. Семиотика. Семантика, 2013, № 2. – С. 95–102
7. Шейгал Е. И. Семиотика политического дискурса: дисс. ... д. филол.н. Волгоград, 2000. – 440 с.
8. Юдина Т. В. Дискурсивное пространство политической речи // СПбГПУ Петербург. –2004. –С. 86–99. – URL: <http://rudocs.exdat.com/docs/index-48313.html>
9. Ярцева В.Н. Лингвистический энциклопедический словарь // МОСКВА «СОВЕТСКАЯ ЭНЦИКЛОПЕДИЯ». –1990. – URL: <http://tapemark.narod.ru/les/590c/html>
10. Карпова А.А. Роль медицинских эвфемизмов в повседневной речи и профессиональной речи медработников (на материале английского языка) // СиБАДИ, Омск. 65 – 2018. – Электрон. Версия печат. публ. – URL: <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=35307501>
11. Zarifovna, R. N. (2022). Types of euphemisms used in everyday life. Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes, 86–89. Retrieved from <http://conferenceseries.info/index.php/online/article/view/52>
12. Ruziyeva, N. (2022). Evfemizmlarning semantik va struktur tahlili (ingliz va o'zbek tillari misolida). центр научных публикаций (buxdu.Uz), 8(8).

https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4295

13. Khudoyberdievna, S. Z. . (2021). ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPTS OF EMOTIONS IN RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGICAL PICTURE OF THE WORLD. Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT, 2, 11-18. <https://literature.academicjournal.io/index.php/literature/article/view/21>.